

RFID with RFIDler

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1. Preface

This paper was written in 2015 as part of a research project at scip AG, Switzerland. It was initially published online at <https://www.scip.ch/en/?labs.20151022> and is available in English and German. Providing our clients with innovative research for the information technology of the future is an essential part of our company culture.

2. Introduction

In *the Internet and the Things* [1] we talked about different protocols used by different devices to communicate with each other, and pictured a very high level overview of how the things should work. In this article, we take a closer look at the RFID standard and play with some tags of type ISO/IEC 18000-2:2009 (125-135kHz), mainly used for identification purposes.

The idea, here, is to take the *EM4000 RFID tags family* as example to look at the various components involved, and then use a very cool tool named *RFIDler* [2] to extract information and quickly emulate or clone a tag. RFIDler is a Kickstarted project I backed last year, created by *Aperture Labs Ltd.* [3]

Now, we will add some pieces to the puzzle and next, time, we'll look at the more interesting ISO/IEC 14443 (Mifare) tags and NFC protocol.

3. "Come On, It's Time to Go"

RFID is an acronym for Radio-Frequency IDentification, the usage of electromagnetic fields to exchange data and – in some cases – power. RFID isn't a new technology, it has been developed in the 1970s. Two actors are involved: a transceiver will identify an object (transponder) *tagged* with a specific ID. Tags can be passive or active (self powered) or mixed.

In this article, we will play only with passive tags. A passive tag is basically composed of a chip – responsible to process the information request – and an antenna. The transponder's antenna receives power from the transceiver's antenna, the transponder's chip sends back the information digitally encoded over an analog modulated signal.

The modulation (*ASK* [4], *FSK* [5], *PSK* [6]) and encoding (*Manchester* [7], *Bi-Phase* [8]) may differ for each tag;

please follow the links and familiarise with the terms, before you continue. The data stored, for this type of tag, are normally some words. Read the *512 bit Read/Write Multi-purpose Contactless Identification Device* [9] description of the EM4205-EM4305 CMOS integrated circuit, to see how the information are organised for this specific chip (UID, Passwords, user data, etc.).

4. "I Do Believe It's Working, Good"

Following infrastructure has been used:

Object	Version	Description
Macbook	Macbook	Macbook
Parallels	11	To run VMs on the Macbook
Kali	2.0	The gaming distro
RFIDler	v022b, 0165-b	To deal with the tags
Tags	n.a.	Some tags to play with

The image *Board Setup* shows the RFIDler board (a) and the setup used to analyse the tags (b). Various try/error showed that some distance between coil and tag is strongly suggested, otherwise, depending on the transponder's coil form, the result may be very strange.

Figure: Board Setup

[10]

Image *RFID Tags* shows the (poor-man's-x-ray version of the) tags used. They are all based on the standard EM4×02 family, but with different form factors and coils.

Figure: RFID Tags

[11]

Connect the board, update firmware, connect to the CLI through terminal.

```
root@kali2:/etc/udev/rules.d# cat 71-rfidler-
lf-cdc-blacklist.rules
# place this file in /etc/udev/rules.d and
run 'sudo udevadm control --reload-rules'
```

```
ACTION!="add|change",
GOTO="mm_usb_device_blacklist_end"
```

```
# bootloader mode (microchip ID)
ATTRS{idVendor}=="04d8"
ATTRS{idProduct}=="003c" MODE:="0666"
SYMLINK+="RFIDlerBL"
```

```
SUBSYSTEM!="tty", GOTO="mm_ignore"
```

```
# openmoko issued id for rfidler-lf
#
http://wiki.openmoko.org/wiki/USB_Product_IDs
ATTRS{idVendor}=="1d50"
ATTRS{idProduct}=="6098" MODE:="0666"
SYMLINK+="RFIDler"
```

```
LABEL="mm_ignore"
ATTRS{idVendor}=="1d50"
ATTRS{idProduct}=="6098",
ENV{ID_MM_DEVICE_IGNORE}="1"
```

```
LABEL="mm_usb_device_blacklist_end"
```

```
root@kali2:/var/log# tail kernel.log
Oct 6 20:09:42 kali2 kernel: [ 2498.962371]
usb 2-1: new full-speed USB device number 3
using uhci_hcd
Oct 6 20:09:42 kali2 kernel: [ 2499.115975]
usb 2-1: New USB device found, idVendor=1d50,
idProduct=6098
Oct 6 20:09:42 kali2 kernel: [ 2499.115980]
usb 2-1: New USB device strings: Mfr=1,
Product=2, SerialNumber=3
Oct 6 20:09:42 kali2 kernel: [ 2499.115982]
usb 2-1: Product: RFIDler-LF
Oct 6 20:09:42 kali2 kernel: [ 2499.115984]
usb 2-1: Manufacturer: Aperture Labs Ltd.
Oct 6 20:09:42 kali2 kernel: [ 2499.115986]
usb 2-1: SerialNumber: 49780C1E00E1
Oct 6 20:09:42 kali2 kernel: [ 2499.125379]
cdc_acm 2-1:1.0: ttyACM0: USB ACM device
```

```
root@kali2:/etc/udev/rules.d# ls -lisa
/dev/ttyACM0
36833 0 crw-rw-rw- 1 root dialout 166, 0 Oct
6 20:13 /dev/ttyACM0
root@kali2:/etc/udev/rules.d# minicom -D
/dev/ttyACM0 -b 115200
```

```
RFIDler> version
0114-beta
```

```
RFIDler>
CTRL-A Z for help | 115200 8N1 | NOR |
Minicom 2.7 | VT102 | Offline | ttyACM0
```

```
rcc@kali2:~/devel/_hardware/RFIDler/project$
git clone
https://github.com/ApertureLabsLtd/RFIDler.gi
t
```

```
rcc@kali2:~/devel/_hardware/RFIDler/project$
tools/mphidflash-1.6-linux-64 -r -w
RFIDler/firmware/Pic32/RFIDler.X/dist/default
/production/RFIDler.X.production.hex
USB HID device found: 503808 bytes free
Device family: PIC32
```

```
Erasing...
Writing hex file
'RFIDler/firmware/Pic32/RFIDler.X/dist/default
t/production/RFIDler.X.production.hex':.....
...
.....
...
..
```

```
rcc@kali2:~/devel/_hardware/RFIDler/project$
minicom -D /dev/ttyACM0 -b 115200
```

```
RFIDler> version
0165-beta
```

And now, the environment is ready.

5. "Is There Anybody in There?"

We have the board, and some tags. Now our goal is to find out information about the hardware, stored data, and emulate or clone it.

5.1. "I Need Some Information, First"

Please get familiar with RFIDler CLI. RFIDler is a specialised board, designed to play with a specific family of RFID cards; do not expect edited manual or complete command reference. You can use Help, DuckDuckGo and the try/error pattern. If you have questions about some functions, clone the firmware source and take a look at the code.

5.2. "Just the Basic Facts"

We have to deal with electromagnetic fields carrying a signal. First step is to find out em characteristics: frequency of the tag and modulation used.

The modulation (*ASK* [12], *FSK* [13], *PSK* [14]) is the method chosen to organise the analog signal in order to transmit something. We are basically interested in the returning wave form, to visually look at the signal and categorise them. Just full-power the tag and look at what comes back. RFIDler can function as signal sniffer, returning the sampled power. The useful CLI command is:

```
*ASKRAW> ANALOGUE 1000
<?xml version="1.0" encoding="UTF-8"?
>
<RFIDler_Samples>
<Description>RFIDler Analogue Coil
Samples</Description>
<Tag>
<Description>Tag
Settings</Description>
<Tag_Type>
<Description>Tag
Type</Description>
<Data>UNIQUE</Data>
</Tag_Type>
<Modulation>
<Description>Modulation
Scheme</Description>
<Data>ASK/OOK</Data>
```


- (e) shows the answer if we energise the tag using the right frequency, in this case 125kHz (fc=800). The signal is clear and the modulation has something to do with amplitude, so it's an ASK.

In a few seconds – all this tests takes approximately 1 minute – we have identified:

- the tag family: ISO/IEC 18000
- the resonance frequency: 125kHz
- the signal modulation: ASK

Now we can try to decode the signal.

Using the same python tool, we tune the *up-trigger* potentiometer to a *reasonable* value, to convert the analog signal to digital signal. Around the half of the signal's amplitude sounds ok, so we choose 150 (5V / 255 * 150 = ~3V): Everything above 3V is 1. Everything below is 0.

```
rcc@kali2:~/devel/_hardware/RFIDler/python$
rfidler.py /dev/ttyACM0 'set tag askraw'
'potset l 0' 'potset h 150' 'set fc 800' 'set
rate 64' plot 500
sending 'SET TAG ASKRAW'
...
```

```
rcc@kali2:~/devel/_hardware/RFIDler/python$
rfidler.py /dev/ttyACM0 'set tag askraw'
'potset l 0' 'potset h 150' 'set fc 800' 'set
rate 64' plot 5000
sending 'SET TAG ASKRAW'
...
```


Figure: Analog to Digital

[16]

(a) shows the decoded signal, in essence how are the hi-low/transitions transformed in digital values. (b) shows the same thing, just for a longer period of time.

Now, how to decide the encoding?

Just try it out :) ... Basically, it depends on the chip. Some chips sends a predefined sequence on startup (Example: the EM4200 family, sends 11111111+1 Parity Bit, so 9x1; this sequence appears only once during the whole sending cycle). Knowing the startup sequence, is possible to check if the encoding is Manchester or Bi-Phase.

```
rcc@kali2:~/devel/_hardware/RFIDler/python$
./rfidler.py /dev/ttyACM0 'set tag em4x02'
'set manchester off' 'set biphas on' 'potset
l 0' 'potset h 150' 'set fc 800' 'set rate
64' plot 640
sending 'SET TAG EM4X02'
sending 'SET MANCHESTER OFF'
sending 'SET BIPHASE OFF'
sending 'POTSET L 0'
```

```
sending 'POTSET H 150'
sending 'SET FC 800'
sending 'SET RATE 64'
...
```

```
rcc@kali2:~/devel/_hardware/RFIDler/python$
./rfidler.py /dev/ttyACM0 'set tag em4x02'
'set manchester off' 'set biphas on' 'potset
l 0' 'potset h 150' 'set fc 800' 'set rate
64' plot 640
sending 'SET TAG EM4X02'
sending 'SET MANCHESTER OFF'
sending 'SET BIPHASE ON'
sending 'POTSET L 0'
sending 'POTSET H 150'
sending 'SET FC 800'
sending 'SET RATE 64'
...
```


Figure: Decoding

[17]

- (a) shows the response with Manchester = ON – the startup sequence looks nice, so maybe it is Manchester encoded.
- (b) shows the response with Bi-Phase = ON – the startup sequence looks strange, so maybe Bi-Phase is wrong.

Figure: Reading the data

[18]

The image *Reading the data* shows the maximum data – that can be display on this web page in a readable form – captured with RFIDler (~9000fc) and the related bit sequence. To feel comfortable with the graph analysis is just matter of number of tags tested to train your eyes to quickly identify the modulation scheme and other interesting parameters. To decode the digital string received, we must know the tag type and the way data is organized in each word; that's the only way to interpret the stream of bits.

7. “Relax”

Using the RFIDler board, we have quickly identified some tags, classified by frequency, modulation, and encoding, extracted information and finally with two simple commands, cloned and emulated.

The importance of short range communication is increasing, and in the next couple of years the number of devices using RFID will explode. It is important to be familiar with the hardware and protocols, look at them from different angles, play with them and try to understand how they work.

RFID cards of type ISO/IEC 18000-2:2009 can be analysed well with the RFIDler board; RFIDler deals with the analog/digital part, and the firmware is open, so it is possible to add personalised functions. Playing with the RFIDler permits us to comfortably explore the strengths and weaknesses of 125-134kHz tags.

P.S.: This lab also demonstrates that *The Aleph of music* [19] applies to anything, anytime! Therefore, it is strongly suggested to read it while *listening* [20] :D

8. External Links

- [1] <https://www.scip.ch/en/?labs.20150813>
- [2] <http://www.rfidler.org>
- [3] <http://aperturelabs.com>
- [4] https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Amplitude-shift_keying
- [5] https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Frequency-shift_keying
- [6] https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Phase-shift_keying
- [7] https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Manchester_code
- [8] https://en.wikipedia.org/w/index.php?title=Differential_Manchester_encoding
- [9] http://www.emmicroelectronic.com/sites/default/files/public/products/datasheets/em4205-4305_ds.pdf
- [10] labs/images/rfidler_board_setup_lg.png
- [11] labs/images/rfidler_rfid_tags_lg.png
- [12] https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Amplitude-shift_keying
- [13] https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Frequency-shift_keying
- [14] https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Phase-shift_keying
- [15] labs/images/rfidler_basic_facts_lg.png
- [16] labs/images/rfidler_analog_to_digital_lg.png
- [17] labs/images/rfidler_decoding_lg.png
- [18] labs/images/rfidler_read_data_lg.png
- [19] https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/The_Wall
- [20] <https://www.youtube-nocookie.com/watch?v=G4i8tzFbTAK>